

Browser Extension "Detector of Manipulations and Subtexts"

Idea Description:

This project represents an intelligent browser extension that allows users to analyze textual data for manipulative techniques, hidden subtexts, and metaphors. The extension operates in real-time, integrates with NLP models, and provides visualization of key frames and meanings.

Functionality:

- 1. Recognition of Manipulative Techniques:**
 - Detects appeals to fear, false generalizations, and factual distortions.
 - Example: *"If Brussels continues its policy, Europe will lose its independence."*
- 2. Metaphor Analysis:**
 - Identifies metaphors (e.g., "swamp," "iron fist") and their manipulative significance.
- 3. Subtext Analysis:**
 - Identifies hidden motives, sarcasm, and irony.
- 4. Data Visualization:**
 - Highlights key phrases in the text.
 - Generates a map of frames showing how the text shapes perception.

Potential Use Cases:

- 1. For general users:**
 - Helps detect disinformation and manipulations online.
- 2. For journalists:**
 - Automates the analysis of subtle textual techniques.
- 3. For researchers:**
 - Enables the study of political discourses and cultural differences.

Unique Features:

1. Combines the analysis of manipulations, subtexts, and metaphors.
2. Provides interactive visualization for clarity.
3. Enables real-time text analysis.

Authorship:

This idea was developed by Arina (Aleksandrovna) Karaseva.